

**CLINICAL STUDY ON SHEETAPITTA W.S.R TO CHRONIC URTICARIA A SINGLE
CASE STUDY**¹*Dr. Vaibhav Bhaskar Jadhav, ²Dr. Sandeep T. Shinde¹3rd Year PG Student, PMT's Ayurved College, Shevgaon and Shri Eknath Rugnalaya Taluka Shevgaon, Dist Ahilyanagar, 414502.²HOD and Guide, Kayachikitsa Department, PMT's Ayurved College, Shevgaon and Shri Eknath Rugnalaya Taluka Shevgaon, Dist Ahilyanagar, 414502.**How to cite this Article:** ¹*Dr. Vaibhav Bhaskar Jadhav, ²Dr. Sandeep T. Shinde. (2026). Clinical Study on Sheetapitta W.S.R To Chronic Urticaria A Single Case Study. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(4), 338–341. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

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ABSTRACT

Sheetapitta is described in classical Ayurvedic texts as a type of *Twak Vikara* characterized by sudden appearance of *Varti-Damshavat Shotha* (raised eruptions), *Kandu* (itching), *Daha* (burning sensation) and sometimes *Shula*. It is considered a *Tridoshaja Vyadhi* with predominance of *Vata* and *Kapha* along with involvement of *Pitta* and *Rakta*. Due to vitiation of these *Doshas*, they circulate through *Rasa* and *Rakta Dhatu* and manifest on the skin. *Nidana* such as *Viruddha Ahara*, excessive intake of spicy, oily and allergenic food, and exposure to cold breeze play an important role in the manifestation of *Sheetapitta*. The clinical features of this condition closely resemble urticaria described in modern medicine. A single case study was conducted on a 38 year old female patient who presented with recurrent reddish elevated rashes associated with severe itching and mild burning sensation all over the body for the past four months. The symptoms were aggravated after consumption of spicy, oily and non-vegetarian food and were more prominent during night time. Based on classical signs and symptoms, the condition was diagnosed as *Sheetapitta*. The patient was managed with Ayurvedic *Shaman Chikitsa* aimed at pacifying the vitiated *Doshas*, purifying *Rakta* and improving *Agni* along with appropriate *Pathya-Apathya*. After the treatment, significant reduction in itching, swelling and erythematous rashes was observed along with decreased recurrence. This case suggests that Ayurvedic *Shaman Chikitsa* based on the principles of *Dosha* and *Samprapti* of *Sheetapitta* can effectively manage the condition and improve the quality of life of the patient.

INTRODUCTION

In Ayurveda, *Sheetapitta* is described as one of the *Twak Vikara* caused due to vitiation of *Vata* and *Kapha Dosha* associated with *Pitta Dosha*. According to *Madhava Nidana*, exposure to cold breeze and intake of *Asatmya Ahara* lead to *Dosha* vitiation, resulting in *Rasa* and *Rakta Dhatu Dushti* and manifestation of symptoms such as *Varti-Damshavat Shotha* (raised eruptions), *Kandu* (itching) and *Daha* (burning sensation) over the skin.^[1] Classical texts also mention related conditions such as *Udarda* and *Kotha* with slight differences in *Dosha* predominance.^[2-5] Due to similarity in etiological factors and clinical features, *Sheetapitta* can be correlated with urticaria, a dermatological condition characterized by erythematous and pruritic wheals caused by increased capillary permeability.^[6,7]

Urticaria affects nearly 15–20% of the population during their lifetime and is commonly triggered by foods, drugs, infections or other allergens.^[8-10] Though it is not life threatening, recurrent itching and eruptions significantly affect the quality of life. In the present single case study, a 38 year old female patient presented with recurrent reddish elevated rashes associated with severe itching and mild burning sensation for four months. Based on classical signs and symptoms the condition was diagnosed as *Sheetapitta*. The patient was managed with Ayurvedic *Shaman Chikitsa* along with *Pathya-Apathya*. After treatment, significant reduction in itching, erythema and frequency of eruptions was observed. The study suggests that *Shaman Chikitsa* based on Ayurvedic principles of *Dosha* and *Samprapti* can effectively manage *Sheetapitta* and improve the patient's quality of life.

CASE REPORT

A 38 year old female patient with medium built reported to OPD and presented with chief complaints of elevated reddish irregular lesions with swelling. The above complaints associated with gradual onset of itching and burning sensation all over the body since 4 months. Itching starts immediately after the consumption of food items like non-veg, spices, citrus fruits, oily food, dry fruits and nuts. The symptoms aggravated more in the night and gradually subside in the morning. The diagnosis was done as *Sheetapitta* on the basis of etiological factors and clinical presentation.

History of present illness

The patient was completely healthy before 4-5 months and gradually developed reddish irregular lesions all over the body. Initially patient neglected the symptoms but when the symptoms got aggravated, she approached to an allopathic hospital and was on antihistamine medication for 4 months. Patient got symptomatic relief but after withdrawal of medication, recurrence of disease occurs. As a result, she decided to take Ayurvedic treatment.

Past history

Patient had no history of any systemic disease, no medical or surgical history.

Personal history Occupation - Housewife

Nidana^[11]

Due to *Sheeta Marutadi Sevan* (exposure to cold wind and cold weather), *Kapha* and *Vata Dosha* gets vitiated and mixed with *Pitta Dosha*. All the three vitiated *Doshas* spreads all over the body and manifests as *Sheetapitta*.

1. *Aharaj Hetu - Atiamla Sevan, Atilavan, Atikatu Sevan, Kshara Sevan, Viruddha Ahar Sevan, Dadhi Sevan.*

2. *Viharaj Hetu - Sheet Maruta Sevan, Bahya Krumi, Keeta Damsha, Chardi Nigrahan, Shishir Ritu, Vastra, Abhushan.*

Ashtavidha Parikshan**Table 1: Ashtavidha Pariksha of the patient.**

Sr.No	Name	Lakshana
1	Nadi (Pulse)	Pitta-Kapha predominant
2	Mala (Stool)	Malavrodha (constipation)
3	Mutra (Urine)	Samyak
4	Jivha (Tongue)	Alpa Saama (slightly coated)
5	Shabda (Speech)	Spashta
6	Sparsha (Touch)	Anushna-Sheeta
7	Druk (Eyes)	Samyak
8	Aakruti (Appearance)	Madhyama

Assessment Criteria

The assessment of the patient was carried out based on improvement in subjective symptoms such as *Kotha*

3. *Nidanaarthakara Roga - Pittaja and Kaphaja Jwara, Sannipatika Roga, Unmarda, Adhoga Amlapitta*

Poorvarup (Premonitory signs)^[12, 13]

Pipasa (Thirst), *Aruchi* (loss of appetite), *Hrillasa* (Nausea), *Dehasaad* (Feeling of tiredness), *Anga Gaurava* (Feeling of heaviness), *Rakta Lochanata* (Redness of eyes).

Rupa (Signs and Symptoms)^[14]

Varti Damshta Samsthana Shotha (Inflammation like an insect bite), *Kandu Bahula* (Severe itching), *Toda Bahula* (Excessive pain like pricking), *Chardi* (Vomiting), *Jvara* (Fever), *Vidaha* (Burning Sensation), *Ksanikotpatti Vinasha*.

Samprapti Ghataka

Dosha: Tridosha

Agni: Mandagni

Vyadhimarga: Bahya

Dushya: Rasa, Rakta

Srotas: Rasavaha, Raktavaha

Srotodushtiprakara: Vimarga Gamana

UdbhavaSthana: Aamashaya

Vyakti Sthana: Tvak

Svabhava: Ashukari

General Examination

Pulse: 89/min

Blood Pressure: 120/70 mmHg

Respiratory Rate: 18 /min

Temperature: 97.8°F

Weight: 64 kg

Height: 5.5 feet

Appetite: reduced (anorexia)

Sleep: disturbed due to itching

(raised wheals), *Kandu* (itching), *Toda* (pricking sensation) and *Daha* (burning sensation).

Table 2: Objective Criteria Urticaria Activity Score (UAS) as per Indian Journal of Dermatology.^[20]

Score	Wheals/24 hrs	Pruritus
0	None	None
1	Mild: <20 wheals over 24 hrs	Mild itching present but not troublesome
2	Moderate: 20–50 wheals over 24 hrs	Moderate itching interfering slightly with routine activities
3	Severe: >50 wheals over 24 hrs or wheals over large body area	Severe itching disturbing daily activities or sleep

Table 3: Subjective Criteria.

Symptoms	Mild	Moderate	Severe
<i>Kotha</i> (Raised oedematous wheals of pink-red colour)	1	2	3
<i>Kandu</i> (Itching)	1	2	3
<i>Toda</i> (Pricking sensation)	1	2	3
<i>Daha</i> (Burning sensation)	1	2	3

Treatment protocol**Table 4: Treatment Protocol.**

Sr.No	Medications	Dosage	Anupana	Duration
1	<i>Haridra Khanda</i>	1 tsf BD	Lukewarm water	3 months
2	<i>Bilwadi Gutika</i>	2 tablets BD	Lukewarm water	1 month
3	<i>Dushivishari Agad</i>	2 tablets BD	Lukewarm water	1 month
4	<i>Avipattikar Churna</i>	1 tsf HS	Lukewarm water	15 day

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

After initiation of treatment, gradual improvement in the patient's clinical symptoms was observed. Noticeable relief started within 15 days of therapy. During the subsequent follow-up visits, significant reduction was noted in symptoms such as *Kandu* (itching), *Daha*

(burning sensation) and *Shotha* (inflammation). By the second visit, the intensity and frequency of itching had markedly decreased and the wheals were reduced. Overall, satisfactory improvement in the patient's condition was recorded during the course of treatment.

Table 5: Observation.

Sr.No	Symptoms	Before Treatment	After Treatment
1	<i>Kotha</i> (raised oedematous pink-red wheals)	3	0
2	<i>Kandu</i> (itching)	3	1
3	<i>Toda</i> (pricking sensation)	2	1
4	<i>Daha</i> (burning sensation)	3	0

Pathya-Apathya*^[21]*1. Pathya**

Jeerna Shali, Jangala Mamsa, Triphala, Madhu, Mudga Yusha, Kulattha Yusha, Ushnodaka, Karkotaka Shaka, Karavellaka Shaka, Moolaka Yusha, Dadima Phala, Shigru Shaka, Moolaka Shaka, Vetragra Phala, Potika Shaka, Lava Rasa and Tittira Rasa.

2. Apathya

Ksheera Vikarani, Chhardi Nigraha, Ikshu Vikarani, Divaswapna, Matsya, Poorva and Dakshina Disha Pavana, Anupa–Audaka Mamsa, Snana, Naveena Madhya, Atapa Sevana, Viruddha Ahara, Vyavaya, Snigdha–Amla–Madhura Dravya, and Guru Annapana.

DISCUSSION

Sheetapitta is a frequently encountered *Twak Vikara* in clinical practice. Various etiological factors such as incompatible diet, environmental triggers and allergens contribute to the development of the disease. Therefore, management should focus on drugs that act on the

underlying causative factors. Ayurveda emphasizes the importance of *Pathya* and *Apathya*, along with *Nidana Parivarjana* (avoidance of causative factors), which forms the primary line of management since dietary habits play an important role in triggering urticarial symptoms.

In contemporary medicine, antihistamines and corticosteroids are widely used for symptomatic relief; however, their prolonged use may produce undesirable side effects. Moreover, recurrence of symptoms is common, highlighting the need for a therapeutic approach that addresses the root cause of the disease.

Haridra Khanda is described in *Bhaishajya Ratnavali* as an effective formulation for the management of *Sheetapitta*. It possesses anti-allergic, antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties, which help in reducing hypersensitivity reactions.^{[15],[16]}

Dushivishari Agada contains ingredients predominantly having *Katu* and *Tikta Rasa*. These properties help in alleviating *Kapha* and *Kleda* from the *Strotas* and act as *Krimihara*, *Kushthahara* and *Vishaghna*.^[17]

Bilwadi Gutika consists of drugs that are mainly *Tikta* and *Katu* in *Rasa* with *Ushna Virya* and *Katu Vipaka*. These attributes make the formulation effective in neutralizing toxins and combating allergic manifestations.^[18]

Avipattikar Churna helps in the elimination of vitiated *Pitta* and *Kapha Dosha* and assists in *Raktaprasadana* by clearing *Kleda* from *Rasa* and *Rakta Dhatu*.^[19]

Thus, Ayurvedic formulations combined with proper *Pathya-Apathya* provide a holistic approach in the management of allergic skin disorders such as *Sheetapitta*.

CONCLUSION

Before starting the treatment, the patient was evaluated using the Urticaria Activity Score (UAS) and was categorized under grade 3 severity. After continuous treatment for one month, there was a notable reduction in both the UAS grading and clinical manifestations. Further improvement was observed after two months of therapy with the prescribed medications. The findings of this single case study indicate that Ayurvedic management through *Shamana Chikitsa* can provide significant relief in patients suffering from *Sheetapitta* and may serve as an effective therapeutic approach.

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